

Analysis of Electrode Positioning Influence on the Forearm for the Classification of Different Hand/Wrist Movements.

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Abstract — Upper limbs myoelectric prosthesis control improvements are fundamental to give back important functions to amputees, e.g. to accomplish daily activities. However, it is very hard to reproduce the number of degrees of freedom as well as of the human limb. In addition, finding the best positioning of electrodes is essential to ensure that the system control is robust. In this paper, two different positions of electrodes throughout subjects' forearm were analyzed, so that a Support Vector Machine model for each position was trained and then compared to find which one is most suitable to perform myoelectric prosthesis control. It was found that the signals of these positions are very different, and the first one (average accuracy of 96.57%) was better than the second (average accuracy of 84.90%).

Keywords—Myoelectric prosthesis control, SVM, EMG.

I. INTRODUCTION

According to Brazil's Health Care System (SUS) database, there were 1478 cases of upper limb amputation in 2018 and 736 only in the first half of 2019 [1]. For people in this situation, returning to daily activities is a difficult and time-consuming task [2]. However, this problem can be reduced by using active prosthesis, which are divided into two groups: body and electrical activation. In this context, myoelectric prosthesis is an example that works with electrical activation and has been a research area on the rise, because its acquisition is usually noninvasive, so that makes it possible its use in clinical applications.

Table 1: Number of cases of upper limb amputation on Brazil according to SUS database.

	Upper limbs Amputations			
	2016	2017	2018	2019*
Number of Cases	1479	1469	1478	736

* For the first semester only.

The use of myoelectric prostheses has been improving day by day, with increasingly modern mechanisms that are able to reproduce precise movements [3]. However, even with the constant advances in research labs with controlled environment, its clinical use is uncommon yet, mainly by the difficulty of user adaptation. One reason is the constant change of positioning of the electrodes. Indeed, electromyographic (EMG) signals change if the electrodes shift from its original position, and it can cause control system malfunction.

Previous works has been analyzed the effects caused trough the electrodes rotation in the performance of the classifier [4], and another works have been trying to fix these problems, e.g. using a higher number of electrodes [5][6]. Indeed, this works related improvements, but these methods do not resolve the effects caused by the translation of

electrodes throughout the subject's forearm. Therefore, this work aims to compare the performance of a SVM-based classifier for two different heights (i.e. P1 and P2) of an electrode set throughout six subject's forearm. There was analyzed the capacity of the SVM model in classify 7 kinds of hand/wrist movements, and then pointed out the best position.

II. METHODS

A. Participants and data acquisition

For the collection of EMG signals, 6 healthy subjects aged between 20 and 23 years old, who had no motor dysfunction were selected. Among them, 5 males and 1 female. MyosystemBr1-P84 Electromyograph (DataHominis Tec Ltda) was used to acquire EMG signals. Four electrode channels were used, which had two active differential electrodes. The sampling rate was set at 2 kHz with Butterworth bandpass filter from 20 to 500 Hz.

B. Electrodes positioning

Before the positioning of the electrodes was defined, the muscles were chosen according to their importance in the execution of each chosen movement. Four muscles were chosen: flexor carpi radialis, flexor carpi ulnaris, extensor carpi ulnaris and extensor digitorum (Figure 1). The electrodes were positioned each on one of the selected muscles.

Figure 1: Positioning of the electrodes around the forearm.

To mark the heights P1 and P2, the total internal measurement of the subject's forearm was performed, measuring from the medial epicondyle of the humerus to the distal groove of the wrist. Then, the total external measurement of the subject's forearm was performed, measuring from the lateral epicondyle of the humerus to the midpoint between the styloid process of the ulna and the styloid process of the radius. Markings were made at 25% of the total length of the inner and outer part and then the two markings were linked forming a circumference around the

subject's forearm, determining P1. From P1, P2 was defined by repeating the same procedure, but with markings at 40% of the total length.

C. Task

The collection consisted of 8 batteries, the first 4 for P1 and the last four for P2. The subjects were instructed to perform six different types of movements, namely wrist flexion (WF), wrist extension (WE), hand supination (HS), hand pronation (HP), hand closure (HC), and pinch gesture (PG). Each collection battery consisted of 60 movements, 10 movements of each type lasting 3 seconds and resting 3 seconds after each movement performed. These movements were presented at random. In all, four 60-movement batteries were performed, totaling 240 movement samples for each position. In addition to these samples, 40 resting (RE) samples (randomly selected from the 240 resting samples collected) were used, totaling 280 samples for each position.

D. Data processing

After all collections, a data preprocessing step was required to filter the DC level and the 60 Hz grid interference. In addition, two more 120 and 180 Hz notch filters were used to attenuate network interference caused by its first two harmonics. To remove the DC level, a 20 Hz high pass digital filter was used. All data processing was done in the Python programming language (version 3.6).

E. Features Extraction

Six different time domain features were extracted for each of the 4 EMG signal channels, getting a total of 24 features. The features chosen were Mean Absolute Value (MAV) (1), Waveform Length (WL) (2), Signal Variance (VAR) (3), Slope Sign Change (SSC) (4), Zero-Crossings (ZC) (5) and Root Mean Square (RMS) (6).

$$MAV = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{k=1}^N |x_k| \quad (1)$$

$$WL = \sum_{k=1}^{N-1} (|x_{k+1} - x_k|) \quad (2)$$

$$VAR = \frac{1}{N-1} \sum_{k=1}^N x_k^2 \quad (3)$$

$$SSC = \sum f(x) \quad (4)$$

Where, $f(x) = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } (x_k > x_{k+1}) \text{ and } (x_k < x_{k-1}) \\ 1, & \text{if } (x_k < x_{k+1}) \text{ and } (x_k > x_{k-1}) \\ 0, & \text{for other conditions} \end{cases}$

$$ZC = \sum f(x) \quad (5)$$

Where, $f(x) = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } (x_k > 0) \text{ and } (x_{k+1} < 0) \\ 1, & \text{if } (x_k < 0) \text{ and } (x_{k+1} > 0) \\ 0, & \text{for other conditions} \end{cases}$

$$RMS = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N} \sum_{k=1}^N x_k^2} \quad (6)$$

Feature scale variations may be a negative factor for classifier performance. Some features may have much larger scales than others, causing the classifier to create a biased model, with distance calculations based on the scale of these

features. To minimize the effects caused by these different scales, each of the 24 features has been normalized to a new scale with values from 0 to 1.

F. Classifier

In this work, it was used SVM model as classifying algorithm. The main reason for this is because this method has been shown very robust, since others works has been proved its applicability in EMG signal classification [7][8][9]. In addition, its use is relatively easy to work into python programming language.

G. Validation

Both sets were trained and tested separately. To perform the classifier training/test, the cross-validation with the 10-Fold method was used. Each set was divided into 10 mutually exclusive subsets of the same size and with 7 evenly distributed classes. Thus 1 subset was used for testing and the other 9 for training. This was repeated 10 times, so each subset was used for testing once.

III. RESULTS

Figure 2 shown the average accuracy of all movement classes to compare the subject performances for both positions P1 and P2.

Figure 2: Average accuracy of all movement classes. The vertical line in each column denotes the standard deviation.

Bellow, in the Table 2: All results for P1. In the lines are the six subjects and in the columns are the seven movement classes. In addition, mean and standard deviation are shown. Table 2 and Table 3 are shown all results after the 10-fold cross-validation. There were calculated the mean and standard deviation in two ways: for all movement classes of each subject and of all subjects for each movement class.

Table 2: All results for P1. In the lines are the six subjects and in the columns are the seven movement classes. In addition, mean and standard deviation are shown.

Position 1 - P1									
Subjects	WE	HC	WF	PG	HP	RE	HS	Mean	Std
S1	1.00	0.95	1.00	0.95	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.99	0.02
S2	0.95	0.94	0.84	0.93	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.95	0.06
S3	1.00	0.97	0.93	0.93	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.98	0.03
S4	1.00	0.85	0.89	0.85	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.94	0.07
S5	1.00	0.98	0.93	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.99	0.03
S6	0.98	0.86	0.95	0.90	1.00	0.95	1.00	0.95	0.05
Mean	0.99	0.93	0.92	0.93	1.00	0.99	1.00	-	-
Std	0.02	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.00	0.02	0.00	-	-

Table 3: All results for P2. In the lines are the six subjects and in the columns are the seven movement classes. In addition, mean and standard deviation are shown.

Position 2 - P2									
Subjects	WE	HC	WF	PG	HP	RE	HS	Mean	Std
S1	1.00	0.81	0.82	0.74	0.95	0.81	0.90	0.86	0.09
S2	0.75	0.87	0.74	0.89	0.89	0.98	0.84	0.85	0.08
S3	1.00	1.00	0.83	0.68	0.82	0.70	0.84	0.84	0.13
S4	1.00	0.81	0.95	0.82	0.88	0.67	0.85	0.85	0.11
S5	1.00	1.00	0.91	0.98	1.00	0.95	0.98	0.97	0.03
S6	0.79	0.74	0.66	0.74	0.78	0.51	0.78	0.71	0.10
Mean	0.92	0.87	0.82	0.81	0.89	0.77	0.87	-	-
Std	0.12	0.11	0.11	0.11	0.08	0.18	0.07	-	-

In addition, it is worth to analyze each subject separately and then compare them. Figures 3 and 4 show the performance after 10-fold cross-validation for the subjects 5 and 6, respectively. There were chosen this subjects because their results were very different comparing to the others subjects.

Figure 3: Subject 5 performance for each movement class. hand/wrist movements (Subject 5)

Figure 4: Subject 6 performance for each movement class. hand/wrist movements (Subject 6)

In order to visualize the EMG signals acquired of each electrode it is presented one of the four batteries for both positions P1 and P2 on Figure 5.

To compare both positions P1 and P2 and assuming whether the accuracies are statistically equal or not, it was realized a Kolmogorov-Smirnov which is a nonparametric test. The p-value found was 0.02597.

Figure 5: EMG signals of subject 4 for both positions P1 and P2. These signals are obtained by (a) one of the 4 batteries of P1 and (b) one of the 4 batteries of P2.

IV. DISCUSSION

The results presented in Figure 2 show that all subjects achieved better performance in P1, being that the average accuracy in P1 and P2 was 96.57 and 84.90 percent, respectively. Moreover, according Kolmogorov-Smirnov test it was possible to assume that P1 and P2 are statistically different with 95% of certainty, since p-value was lower than 0.05, rejecting then the null hypothesis. This shows that EMG signals collected in P1 has a tendency to be better than in P2. This makes sense, because P1 is located on muscle belly, where EMG signals have then maximum range. On the other hand, P2 is located above P1, and the range EMG signals acquired in this position is relatively lower. This can be seen on Figure 5, so that channels 1, 2 and 4 for P1 have greater amplitude than for P2 and only channel 3 has similar amplitude for both positions.

Analyzing the figure 2, we can see that average accuracy of subjects 1, 2, 3 and 5 have a standard deviation for P2 higher than for P1. The reason for this is because the subjects did not have good performance for some movement classes, for example, subject 3 had a great performance for the movement classes WE and HC, moderate performance for WF, HP and HS, and low performance for PG and RE. The low performance can be because EMG signal amplitude of the muscles responsible to do these movements were lower, and can be detrimental to the classifier.

We also analyzing the individual performances of the subjects 5 and 6. Both subjects had peculiar performances. On the one hand, subject 5 had the best performance for both positions, achieving an average accuracy of 98.71 and 97.43 percent for P1 and P2, respectively. On the other hand, subject 6 had a great performance for P1 (94.86%), however, this subject had the lowest performance for P2 (71.43%). A comparison between P1 and P2 for each movement was presented on figures 3 and 4, and we can see that P2 was as

good as P1 for the subject 5, but very different for the subject 6.

It is hard to find the best position to acquire EMG signals yet, principally because each person has its own anatomy, and these results demonstrate this. Thus, it is important augment the number of subjects to achieve generic results.

V. CONCLUSIONS

According to the results presented, we assume that P1 demonstrated to be the recommended position for myoelectric prosthesis control and we prove it statistically. However, it is necessary to improve some aspects, for example, augment the number of subjects to get more robust statistical analysis, the number of positions and analyzing in which one the classifier works better. In addition, it is possible to analyze another features (e.g. frequency domain) rather than only in time domain.

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